

A Case Study of Small Molecules as Antimalarials: 2-Amino-1-Phenylethanol (APEs) derivatives

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The human biological samples were sourced ethically and their research use was in accord with the terms of the informed consents. All animal studies were ethically reviewed and carried out in accordance with European Directive 2010/63/EU and the GSK Policy on the Care, Welfare and Treatment of Animals.

1. General Synthetic Route

These compounds were prepared from both the commercially available ketone and the also commercially available amines, and the corresponding reductor agents were sodium borohydride, Sodium bis(methoxyethoxy) aluminium hydride (Red-Al) or (tetrahydro-1H-furan-1-ium-1-yl)trihydroborate as appropriate. Similar synthetic protocol to describe in bupropion synthesis (US6337328B1, *Synt. Comm.* **2010**, *40*, 1566-1573., *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry* **2000**, *11*, 3659-3663).

Synthesis of 19. *Threo*-amino-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propan-1-ol as trifluoroacetic salt.

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It was stirred solution of 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde (200 μ l, 1.493 mmol), nitroethane (206 μ l, 2.87 mmol) and triethylamine (7.96 μ l, 0.057 mmol) in Ethanol (240 μ l) with Water(120 μ l). This mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature in the dark. The mixture was ice-cooled and acetic acid (6.58 μ l, 0.115 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture. Alcohol and excess nitroethane were evaporated under vacuum. Water (30ml) was added and nitro alcohol extracted with ethyl acetate, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and the solvent evaporated to give the desired product, 2-nitro-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol, as a colourless oil.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $d\text{-CDCl}_3$) δ ppm: 7.76 (m, 3H); 7.61 (m, 3H); 5.6 (d, 0.5H); 5.2 (d, 1H); 4.89-4.78 (m, 1.5H); 2.9-2.7 (m, 1.5H); 1.59 (d, 2H); 1.46 (d, 3H).

To a solution of 2-nitro-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol (300 mg, 1.204 mmol) in Ethanol (10 mL) was added 10% Pd (C) (55 mg, 0.052 mmol). The mixture was reacted in a Parr apparatus under 50 psi of Hydrogen. 7h30min later, reaction was filtered through Celite and the filtrate was concentrate and purified on aminopropyl (NH₂) 5g cartridge using a 0-12% mixture of dichloromethane/methanol over 15 mins. The appropriate fraction was evaporated in vacuum to give 115 mg of a crude product as colourless oil. The mixture of diastereomers was purified by HPLC Preparative. HPLC_PREP_Agilent 1100. COLUMN: SUNFIRE_19x150mm using an isocratic method (15%): acetonitrile (+ 0.1%TFA)-water (+ 0.1%TFA) 15:85 over 35 mins. The appropriate fractions were combined and evaporated in vacuum to lead a pure mixture of enantiomers (RR/SS) 2-amino-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propan-1-ol as trifluoroacetic salt (Based on $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ experiments, it has been determined that the molar relation of TFA/compound is 1)

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ ppm: 7.96 (br.s, 2H), 7.84 (d, 2H), 7.69 (d, 2H), 6.5 (d, 1H), 4.64 (m, 1H), 1.08 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 220(MH⁺). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (216 nm), Rt: 0.98 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7 μ 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Synthesis of 20. *Threo*-2-(methyl (tert-pentyl) amino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol

A round-bottom flask was charged with *Threo*-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol hydrochloride (68 mg, 0.118 mmol), formic acid (0.049 mL, 1.175 mmol) (90% solution in H₂O) and formaldehyde (0.035 mL, 0.470 mmol) (37% solution in H₂O) in sequence

at rt., the resulting mixture was heated to reflux and more formaldehyde was added to completion. The solution was allowed to cool to rt., and aq NaOH was added until pH > 8. The aqueous layer was then extracted with DCM (3x25 mL). The organic layer was washed with brine (50 mL) and dried over MgSO₄. Removal of the solvent in vacuum and purified on a 2g silica cartridge affording 26mg of expected product.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 7.88 (d, 2H); 7.77(d, 2H); 4.43 (d, 1H); 3.3-3.2 (m, 1H); 2.22 (s, 3H); 2-1.6 (m, 2H); 1.44 (s, 3H); 1.37 (s, 3H); 1.24 (t, 3H); 1.18 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 305(MH⁺). Purity was determined as > 85 % by LC/MS (219 nm), Rt: 1.33 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Synthesis of 23. 2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) ethanol

2-bromo-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) ethanone (190 mg, 0.630 mmol) was dissolved in MeOH at 0°C, and NaBH₄ (47.7 mg, 1.260 mmol) was added in small portions. It remained at 0°C reaching slowly room temperature, and it remained at room temperature overnight. 5ml of water were added, it remained stirring 15 minutes, and the reaction mixture was concentrated to dryness. This crude was partitioned between water and ethyl acetate. Organic layer was washed with water and with brine and organic layer was concentrated to dryness obtaining 2-bromo-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)ethanol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 7.7 (d, 1H); 7.6 (m, 2H); 7.48 (dd, 1H); 4 (m, 1H); 3.3 (m, 1H); 2.83 (m, 1H).

To a solution of 2-bromo-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) ethanol in EtOH, 2-methylpropan-2-amine was added. The mixture was heated at 100°C for 25min in a MW reactor. 0.2ml of amine was added and the mixture was heated for 10min more under the same microwave conditions. Solvent was removed and the resulting oil was purified by chromatography (Hex/EtOAc), affording 26 mg of compound 2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) ethanol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.71 (s, 1H), 7.48 (s, 2H), 4.58 (dd, 1H), 2.94 (dd, 1H), 2.48 (dd, 1H), 1.11 (s, 9H). [ES+ MS] m/z 296 (MH⁺).

Synthesis of 28 & 29.

2-amino-1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)ethanol (0.971 mmol) and the corresponding commercial aldehyde were mixed 1:1 in 1,2-dichloroethane (3 mL). DIPEA was added when necessary and the reaction was stirred for 2h, then sodium triacetoxyhydroborate (1.39 eq.) was added. When the reaction had finished it was evaporated under vacuum; the crude was dissolved in DCM and quenched with water, organic phase was back extracted and washed with brine, dried over MgSO₄, filtered and concentrated affording a crude that was triturated with a mixture of DCM/Hexane, a white solid precipitated, it was filtered and washed with hexane obtaining desired compounds.

2. Separation of *Erythro* mixtures.

Tert-butylchlorodimethylsilane (0.074 mL, 0.430 mmol) and 1H-imidazole (26.6 mg, 0.391 mmol) were added to a solution of 2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propan-1-ol (113 mg, 0.391 mmol) in N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (0.5 mL), was refluxed for two hour, more tert-butylchlorodimethylsilane (0.074 mL, 0.430 mmol) and 1H-imidazole (26.6 mg, 0.391 mmol) were added and refluxed additional two hours. The reaction reached room temperature, and it was diluted with water and ether was added. Organic phase was extracted washed with brine, dried over MgSO₄, filtered and solvent was evaporated under vacuum affording a crude. This crude was purified in silice cartridge (10g) and eluted with AcOEt/MeOH 0-10% in 10min, affording a mixture of two pairs of enantiomers (RS/SR and RR/SS).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.55 (d, 2H); 7.43 (d, 2H); 4.57 (d, 1H); 2.82 (m, 1H); 1.34-1 (m, 2H); 0.95 (m, 6H); 0.92 (s, 9H); 0.8 (t, 3H); 0.09 (s, 3H); 0.01 (s, 3H).

And then, eluted with DCM/EtOAc 0-15% in 25 min. Two pure fractions were obtained and the one corresponded to *erythro* mixture was used in the next step of the synthesis

N-((1R,2S)-1-((tert-butyl)dimethylsilyloxy)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propan-2-yl)-2-methylbutan-2-amine compound with N-((1S,2R)-1-((tert-butyl)dimethylsilyloxy)-1-(4-(1,1-difluoroethyl)phenyl)propan-2-yl)-2-methylbutan-2-amine (1:1) (41mg, 102mmol,) and tetrabutylammonium fluoride (0.056 mL, 0.056 mmol) were dissolved in Tetrahydrofuran (THF) (1 mL), for four hours.. Solvent was evaporated and was purified by preparative HPLC (column: SUNFIRE 19x150 mm. GRADIENT: WATER-ACN 90:10; 3min 90:10; 15min 0:100; 20min 0:100; Wavelength: 210nm) affording a colorless oil and then silice cartridge (2g) affording 30mg of Erythro-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol 2, 2, 2-trifluoroacetate as a colorless oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 8.38 (br.s, 1H); 8.17 (br.s, 1H); 7.84 (d, 2H), 7.73 (d, 2H), 6.43 (br.s, 1H), 5.17 (br.s, 1H), 3.75 (br.s, 1H), 1.83 (c, 2H), 1.4 (d, 6H), 1.07 (d, 3H), 0.98 (t, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH⁺). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (220 nm), Rt: 1.14 (UPLC CSH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

3. Chiral separation conditions

Chiral separation details of compound 6 to obtain 13 and 14 and 7 to obtain 15 and 16:

Chiral LC Conditions. Analytical: Columns ASH, 5μm, Column Dimensions 4.6x250mm, Mobile phase A 99%Hexanes(0.1%Diethylamine (DEA)), Mobile phase B 1% Isopropanol (IPA), Instrumentation Agilent Analytical LC/MS, UV wavelength 225, 275nm, Final Conditions if Isocratic 1%IPA/99%Hexanes(0.1%DEA)

Chiral LC Conditions. Prep: Column and Dimensions 30X250mm ASH, Column Serial Number ASH0SALB002-703221, Mobile phase A Hexanes (0.1%DEA), Mobile phase B IPA, Instrumentation Agilent prep LC/MS, Instrumentation Agilent prep LC/MS, Flow Rate 35ml/min, UV wavelength 275nm, Final Conditions if Isocratic 1%IPA/99%hexanes(0.1%DEA), *0.1M HCl was added to each collection flask, Sample Prep— Diluent Methanol (MeOH), Concentration (50mg/1mL), Load (1mg)/Injection.

RPLC conditions analytical: Column 4.6x150mm, Gemini C18, Column Dimensions 4.6x250mm, Mobile phase A H₂O, Mobile phase B Acetonitrile (ACN), Instrumentation Agilent Analytical LC/MS, Flow Rate 1mL/min, Final Conditions 10-90%ACN-H₂O.

RPLC conditions Prep: Column Gemini C18, Dimensions 21.20x100mm, Column Serial Number 470978-2, Mobile phase A H₂O, Mobile phase B CAN, Instrumentation Agilent prep LC/MS, Flow Rate 20mL/min, UV wavelength 225nm, Final Conditions 10-90%ACN-H₂O.

Chiral separation details of compound 9 to obtain 17 and 18.

Threo isomer was dissolved in DCM and washed with sat K₂CO₃ solution and H₂O. The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo to provide the corresponding free base. Now, the compound as free base was resolved into its two enantiomers by LC/MS: CHIRALPAK AY-RH (250x20mm, 5 μ m) using 10 mM ammonium acetate pH = 9 with DEA / ACN (40 / 60) as eluent. Appropriate fractions were combined and frozen-dry. Residual DEA was removed under vacuum (heating at 50 °C) to obtain the enantiomers. Then, were dissolved in 3 mL of diethylether and 0.1 mL of hydrogen chloride (2M in ether). It was stirred for 1 hour and then the solid was collected by filtration to give compounds 17 and 18.

4. Spectroscopical/purity data

Compound 6. *Threo*-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 8.69 (br.s, 1H), 7.97 (br.s, 1H), 7.84 (d, 2H), 7.76 (d, 2H), 6.65 (br.s, 1H), 4.65 (d, 1H), 3.62 (m, 1H), 1.82 (m, 2H), 1.39 (m, 2H), 1.06 (m, 3H), 0.96 (m, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (281 nm), Rt: 1.18 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 7. *Threo*-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 8.47 (s, 1H); 7.99 (s, 1H); 7.95 (s, 1H); 7.80 (d, 1H); 7.74 (d, 1H); 6.50 (s, 1H); 4.62 (d, 1H); 3.55 (s, 1H); 1.33 (s, 9H); 1.0 (d, 3H).

[ES+ MS] m/z 310 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (223 nm), Rt: 1.18 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 8. *Erythro*-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol 2, 2, 2-trifluoroacetate.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 8.38 (br.s, 1H); 8.17 (br.s, 1H); 7.84 (d, 2H), 7.73 (d, 2H), 6.43 (br.s, 1H), 5.17 (br.s, 1H), 3.75 (br.s, 1H), 1.83 (c, 2H), 1.4 (d, 6H), 1.07 (d, 3H), 0.98 (t, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (220 nm), Rt: 1.14 (UPLC CSH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 9. *Threo*-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(tert-pentylamino) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.48 (d, 1H), 7.46 (d, 1H), 7.19 (dd, 1H), 4.81 (d, 1H), 3.26 (m, 1H), 1.95 (m, 2H), 1.53 (s, 6H), 1.34 (d, 3H), 1.08 (t, 3H).

[ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (225 nm), Rt: 1.62 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 10. *Erythro*-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(tert-pentylamino) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 8.38 (s, 2H), 7.76 (d, 1H), 7.73 (d, 1H), 7.51 (dd, 1H), 6.35 (d, 1H), 5.14 (br.s, 1H), 3.77 (br.s, 1H), 1.84 (c, 2H), 1.4 (d, 6H), 1.05 (d, 3H), 0.98 (t, 3H).

[ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (225 nm), Rt: 1.16 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 11. *Threo*-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm: 9.53 (bs, 1H), 8.16 (bs, 1H), 7.47-7.44 (m, 2H), 7.18 (dd, 1H), 5.89 (bs, 1H), 4.76 (d, 1H), 3.23 (m, 1H), 1.60 (s, 9H), 1.32 (d, 3H).

[ES+ MS] m/z 276 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (225 nm), Rt: 1.01 (UPLC CSH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 12 *Erythro*-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 9.03 (bs, 1H), 8.80 (bs, 1H), 7.50 (d, 1H), 7.44 (d, 1H), 7.24 (dd, 1H), 5.48-5.31 (m, 2H), 3.40 (m, 1H), 1.63 (s, 9H), 1.32 (d, 3H).

[ES+ MS] m/z 276 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (224 nm), Rt: 0.99 (UPLC CSH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH₃COO NH₄ 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 13 (1S, 2S)-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.6 (d, 2H), 7.5 (d, 2H), 3.95 (d, 1H), 1.49-1.43 (c, 9H), 1.4 (s, 2H), 1.1 (d, 6H), 1.05 (d, 3H), 0.93 (t, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290 (MH+). Purity was

determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (219 nm), Rt: 1.42 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +277.4^\circ$ (c = 0.36 wt%, $\lambda = 405\text{nm}$, CDCl₃).

Compound 14 (1R, 2R)-2-(tert-pentylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.6 (d, 2H), 7.5 (d, 2H), 3.95 (d, 1H), 1.49-1.43 (c, 9H), 1.4 (s, 2H), 1.1 (d, 6H), 1.05 (d, 3H), 0.93 (t, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290(MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (219 nm), Rt: 1.42 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -296.7^\circ$ (c = 0.22 wt%, $\lambda = 405\text{nm}$, CDCl₃).

Compound 15 (1S, 2S)-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm: 7.96 (m, 1H); 7.81 (m, 1H); 7.75 (m, 1H), 6.53 (br.s, 1H); 4.62 (d, 1H); 3.55 (m, 1H), 1.33 (s, 9H), 1.01 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 310 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (230 nm), Rt: 1.39 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +300^\circ$ (c = 0.24 wt%, $\lambda = 405\text{nm}$, CDCl₃).

Compound 16 (1R, 2R)-2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(4-chloro-3-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ ppm: 7.96 (m, 1H); 7.81 (m, 1H); 7.76 (m, 1H), 6.47 (br.s, 1H); 4.61 (d, 1H); 3.55 (m, 1H), 1.33 (s, 9H), 1.01 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 310 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (230 nm), Rt: 1.38 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -211^\circ$ (c = 0.92 wt%, $\lambda = 405\text{nm}$, CDCl₃).

Compound 17 (1S, 2S)-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(tert-pentylamino) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 9.48 (br.s, 1H), 7.83 (br.s, 1H), 7.46(m, 2H), 7.19 (m, 1H), 5.85(br.s, 1H), 4.83(br.s, 1H), 3.30 (br.s, 1H), 1.98 (d, 2H), 1.54 (s, 6H), 1.34 (br.s, 3H), 1.05 (d,3H), 0.93 (t,3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290(MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (225 nm), Rt: 1.17 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 18 (1R, 2R)-1-(3, 4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(tert-pentylamino) propan-1-ol hydrochloride.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 9.48 (br.s, 1H), 7.83 (br.s, 1H), 7.46(m, 2H), 7.19 (m, 1H), 5.85(br.s, 1H), 4.83(br.s, 1H), 3.30 (br.s, 1H), 1.98 (d, 2H), 1.54 (s, 6H), 1.34 (br.s, 3H), 1.05 (d,3H), 0.93 (t,3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 290(MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (225 nm), Rt: 1.18 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 21 *Threo*-2-(phenylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 7.73 (m, 4H); 7.13 (dd, 2H); 6.72 (d, 2H); 6.6 (t, 1H); 4.82 (d, 1H); 3.70 (m, 1H); 1.0 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 296(MH+). Purity was determined as > 90 % by LC/MS (219 nm), Rt: 1.86 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 22 *Threo*-2-(cyclohexylamino)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl) phenyl) propan-1-ol.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d-CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.59 (d, 2H), 7.44 (d, 2H), 4.76 (br.s, 1H), 3.14 (m, 1H), 2.6 (m, 1H), 2-1 (m, 10H). [ES+ MS] m/z 302 (MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (217 nm), Rt: 1.50 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

Compound 24 2-(tert-butylamino)-1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)ethanol hydrochloride

[ES+ MS] m/z 261(MH+).

Compound 25 2-(cyclohexylamino)-1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl) ethanol.

[ES+ MS] m/z 287(MH+).

Compound 26 2-(cycloheptylamino)-1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)ethanol hydrochloride.

[ES+ MS] m/z 302(MH+).

Compound 27 2-(cyclooctylamino)-1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)ethanol hydrochloride

[ES+ MS] m/z 316(MH+).

Compound 30 2-(tert-butylamino)-1-phenylpropan-1-ol

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ ppm: 7.29 (s, 5H), 7.26 (brs, 1H), 4.94 (brs, 1H), 4.40 (s, 1H), 1.01 (s, 2H), 6.4 (br.s, 1H), 0.97 (s, 9H), 0.78 (d, 3H). [ES+ MS] m/z 208(MH+). Purity was determined as > 95 % by LC/MS (211 nm), Rt: 0.94 (UPLC BEH C18 1.7u 2.1x50mm, CH3COO NH4 50mM / Acetonitrile, pH 6.6).

5. Plasma Protein Binding

Equilibrium dialysis using the Rapid Equilibrium Dialysis (RED) device is the used technique to determine the *in vitro* plasma protein binding. The device consists of 48 disposable dialysis (molecular weight cut-off 8,000 daltons) inserts. Separation of free compound from protein bound material will be achieved by dialysis of the sample through the membrane. Samples are analysed by HPLC-MS/MS to determine the concentration in plasma and buffer.

$$\% \text{ Unbound} = \frac{[\text{Buffer}]}{[\text{Plasma}]} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Bound} = 100 - \% \text{ Unbound}$$

6. Microsomal Stability

Incubations are performed with appropriate cofactors and a known drug concentration over a specified time-course. Samples are removed from the incubation at various time-points and analysed by LC-MS/MS for parent drug. The rate of parent depletion can then be scaled up to give an intrinsic clearance (CL_{int}) value which can then be used to predict the metabolic contribution to total blood clearance.

- **cofactor have been used?** NADPH
- **What concentration of drug has been evaluated?** 0.5 uM
- **HPLC conditions?**

Acquity UPLC-System
Spectrometrer

API 2000 Qtrap Mass

Column: Acquity BEH C18 50x2.1mm 1.7um

Phase A: ammonium formate 20mM

Phase B: ACN

Flow: 0.3ml/min

Ion Mode: ESI(+)

Source Temp: 500°C

GS1: 50

GS2: 50

Scan type: MRM

Time	A	B
0	90	10
0.5	90	10
1	10	90
1.49	10	90
1.5	90	10

Vinj: 10ul

Injection mode: partial loop with needle overfill

Column temperature: 40°C

- **Which time-point?** 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27 and 30 minutes.

7. *P. falciparum* growth inhibition assay.

The sensitivity of *P. falciparum* infected erythrocytes to various drugs is determined by triplicate using the [3H]hypoxanthine incorporation method with an inoculum of 0.5% parasitemia (ring stage) and 2% hematocrit. The parasites were grown in RPMI 1640, 25 mM HEPES and supplemented with 5% Albumax. Plates are incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂, 5% O₂, 90% N₂. After 24h of incubation, [3H]hypoxanthine is added and plates are incubated for another 24 h. After that period, plates are harvested on a glass fiber filter using a TOMTEC Cell harvester 96. Filters are dried and melt on scintillator sheets and the bound radioactivity is quantified by use of a Wallac Microbeta Trilux (Model 1450 LS- Perkin Elmer). IC₅₀s are determined using Grafit 5 program (Grafit program; Erithacus Software, Horley, Surrey, United Kingdom).

8. Parasite reduction ratio (PRR) assay.

The methods used for investigation of parasitocidal kinetics, determination of PRR (parasite reduction ratio or number of parasites the drug can kill in a parasite life cycle) and the time required to kill 99.9% of the initial population of parasites in vitro, that is, PCT_{99.9%} (parasite clearance time), have been described previously by Sanz *et al.*¹⁴